

Halide Alkoxides of Tin(IV)

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Halide alkoxides of tin (iv) of the type $\text{SnX}_n(\text{OR})_{4-n}$ (where $n=1, 2$, and 3 and $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ and Br) have been prepared by treating tin isopropoxide isopropanolate with acyl halides in stoichiometric ratios. Four or more moles of acyl halides yield derivatives, $\text{SnCl}_{3-5}(\text{OAc})_{0-5}$, Pr^iOH , Pr^iOAc and SnBr_4 . Reaction of stannic ethoxide with 4 moles of acetyl chloride affords the adduct, $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{EtOAc}$. Reactions of isopropoxide with hydrogen halide and stannic halides with isopropanol and organic esters have also been studied. Radical-interchange reaction involving chloride alkoxides is demonstrated.

Considerable work has been done on the halide alkoxides of aluminium¹⁻³, titanium³⁻⁵, zirconium⁶⁻⁸, germanium⁹, and vanadium¹⁰. No such study appears to have been carried out for Sn(iv) except the one dealing with reactions of stannic halides with alcohols¹¹⁻¹³. Adducts of stannic halides, especially chloride, with ester molecules are well known¹⁴⁻¹⁹.

In a detailed study of the reaction involving acetyl chloride and bromide on the stannic isopropoxide, $\text{Sn}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$, Pr^iOH , the following reactions were found to take place

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quantitatively. No hydrogen halide could, however, be detected from the possible side reaction between acyl halide and the isopropanol of addition.

Unlike chloride alkoxides of titanium and germanium, the tin compounds are not stable under reduced pressure and bromide alkoxides, in general, are less stable than chloride alkoxides. Like zirconium, these lose the addendum isopropanol to give rise to solvate-free compound in some cases, when heated under reduced pressure.

Reaction of acetyl chloride in higher molar ratios (1:4 or 1:6) yielded a product, $\text{SnCl}_{1.5}(\text{OAc})_{0.5} \cdot \text{Pr}^i \text{OH} \cdot \text{Pr}^i \text{OAc}$, probably through the steps:

In case of acetyl bromide, the final product of such a reaction is always the stannic bromide. To confirm these conclusions, it has been shown that stannic chloride reacts with isopropyl acetate, forming $\text{SnCl}_{1.5}(\text{OAc})_{0.5} \cdot 1.5\text{Pr}^i \text{OAc}$. The reaction of $\text{Sn}(\text{OEt})_4$ with 4 (>4) moles of acetyl chloride provided the well-known $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{EtOAc}$. The ethyl acetate is less reactive than isopropyl acetate towards stannic chloride. This appears to be in conformity with the reactivity of anhydrous chlorides towards *t*-butyl acetate as reported in the case of aluminium and zirconium⁹. The reactions of tin(IV) *t*-butoxide with acyl halide appear to be rather complex, but the reaction of stannic chloride with *t*-butyl acetate affords a well-defined product, $\text{SnCl}_4(\text{OOCMe})_2$ by the reaction:

The stannic bromide with isopropyl acetate provided a clear solution with a slight evolution of heat, but no addition product could be isolated from the system. Stannic bromide was found to interact with isopropanol to furnish, $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 3.5\text{Pr}^i \text{OH}$. It appears to follow the general sequence²⁰ for the formation of co-ordination compounds by the tetrahalides of Si, Ge, Sn, Sn, $\gg$ Ge > Si and F > Cl > Br > I.

The action of hydrogen halide with stannic isopropoxide afforded $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Pr}^i \text{OH}$ in agreement with the generalisation suggested previously²¹. In the case of hydrogen bromide, no definite compound could, however, be isolated.

The stoichiometric nature of these rapid reactions involving acyl halide suggests occurrence of radical interchangeability between halide alkoxides. This has been proved by refluxing tin dichloride di-isopropoxide and tin isopropoxide together in the molar ratio of 1:1, when the monochloride compound crystallises on cooling.

In this reaction, tin shows an analogy to the corresponding zirconium system, but higher bromide products of zirconium⁷ appear to be more reactive than those of tin.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Analytical procedures and methods of drying the reagents have been described before²². Tin(IV) isopropoxide isopropanolate, prepared from *t*-butoxide²³, was purified by repeated crystallisation from isopropanol. Stannic ethoxide was prepared from *t*-butoxide by alcoholic interchange. Stannic halides, prepared by the direct interaction of the elements, were freshly distilled before use. Acyl halides and organic esters were fractionated directly into the reaction systems. Acetoxy group was estimated by titrating the weighed sample with *N*/10-NaOH, using phenolphthalein. It was initially tested by a number of blank experiments that stannic chloride required 4.02 equivalents of alkali. Further, it was found that the first drop of NaOH solution, when added to isopropyl acetate, developed immediate colour to phenolphthalein.

Reaction between Stannic Alkoxides and Acyl Halides.—To a solution of stannic alkoxide in dry benzene was added a calculated amount of acetyl chloride or bromide. The reactions were highly exothermic (relatively high in acetyl chloride). The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 45 min. at 90–100°. The volatile fractions were removed under reduced pressure (28–38°/0.1–1.5 mm). The results of these experiments are recorded in Table I.

Reaction of Stannic Halide with Isopropyl Acetate.—Isopropyl acetate (6.26 g.) reacted exothermically with stannic chloride (3.9 g.) After refluxing and drying, a white solid (4.1 g.) was obtained. [Found: Sn, 27.9; Cl, 29.7; alkali, 3.99 moles. $\text{SnCl}_{3.5}(\text{OAc})_{0.5}$, 1.5 Pr^iOAc requires Sn, 27.89; Cl, 29.1%; alkali, 4.0 moles]. It sublimed (35°/0.5 mm) unchanged and a white solid could be trapped in a cooled receiver. Mixing of isopropyl acetate (8.3 g.) and stannic bromide (5.05 g.) led to evolution of a slight amount of heat. When the solvent was stripped, a light brown viscous liquid (4.9 g.) was left. (Found: Sn, 27.4; Br, 72.0. Calc. for SnBr_2 : Sn, 27.1; Br, 72.9%).

Reactions of Stannic Isopropoxide with Hydrogen Halide.—HCl gas was bubbled into stannic isopropoxide, $\text{Sn}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ (3.27 g.) in benzene (40 g.) till the reaction mixture cooled down to the room temperature. After drying under reduced pressure, a white solid (2.81 g.) was obtained. (Found: Sn, 32.1; Cl, 39.5; Pr^iOH , 31.0. $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ requires Sn, 31.2; Cl, 37.3; Pr^iOH , 31.5%).

A similar reaction of HBr with stannic isopropoxide (3.08 g.), provided an immiscible, yellowish brown, oily liquid (3.6 g.). (Found: Sn, 19.2; Br, 57.0%; ratio 1:4.4).

Reaction between Stannic Bromide and Isopropanol.—The white solid (3.1 g.) was obtained after removing excess isopropanol from the mixture of stannic bromide (4.6 g.) and isopropanol (18.0 g.), which was refluxed as usual. (Found: Sn, 18.08; Br, 48.3; ratio, 1:3.96. $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 3.5 \text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ requires Sn, 18.03; Br, 49.2%). A fuming solid with the same analysis (1.8 g.) volatilised at the room temperature (37°) when it (2.1 g.) was evacuated at 1.0 mm.

Reaction between Stannic Isopropoxide and Dichloride Di-isopropoxide.—The reaction mixture of tin isopropoxide (2.05 g.) and dichloride di-isopropoxide (1.82 g.) in isopropanol

TABLE I

Reaction mixture.	Molar ratio.	Nature of the product.	Found		Requires		Remarks.				
			Sn: ClorBr. Pr-OH.	Alkali.	Sn.	ClorBr. Pr-OH. Alkali.					
Sn(OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (3.93 g.) CH ₃ COCl (0.73 g.) benzene (24.0 g.)	1 : 1	SnCl ₂ (OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (3.60 g.) white solid	30.70%	0.21%	60.5%	..	30.3%	9.05%	61.1%	..	Crystallizes from benzene and Pr-OH; loses isopropanol (0.5 mm/80-90°) of addendum.
Sn(OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (3.77 g.) CH ₃ COCl (1.48 g.) benzene (24.8 g.)	1 : 2	SnCl ₂ (OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (3.3 g.) white solid	31.90	18.90	47.9	..	32.2	19.20	49.0	..	
Sn(OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (3.74 g.) CH ₃ COCl (2.11 g.) benzene (28.0 g.)	1 : 3	SnCl ₂ (OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (3.0 g.) white solid	34.61	30.70	34.8	..	34.4	30.90	34.9	..	Crystallized as needles from benzene.
Sn(OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (4.07 g.) CH ₃ COCl (3.09 g.) benzene (33.0 g.)	1 : 4	SnCl ₂ (OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH. (4.0 g.) colorless viscous liquid	26.70	26.10	12.3*	3.08M	27.3	28.50	13.8	4.0M	On distillation (37°/0.5 mm), a white solid was obtained. [Found: Sn, 27.7; Cl, 32.0; Pr-OH, 12.9; ratio, 1:3.85. SnCl ₂ . Pr-OH. Pr-OAc requires Sn, 28.07; Cl, 33.5; Pr-OH, 14.2%].
Sn(OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (2.88 g.) CH ₃ COCl (3.26 g.) benzene (8.0 g.)	1 : 6	SnCl ₂ (OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH. (2.8 g.) brown viscous liquid	27.50	29.30	12.1	3.99	27.3	28.50	13.8	2.0	It solidifies as long needles.
Sn(OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (4.09 g.) CH ₃ COBr (1.20 g.) benzene (18.0 g.)	1 : 1	SnBr(OPr) ₂ . Pr-OH (4.2 g.) white solid	27.70	18.84	..	..	27.2	18.30	..	..	Crystallizes from isopropanol.

TABLE I (contd.)

Reaction mixture.	Molar ratio.	Nature of the product.	Found		Analysis		Requires	Remarks.
			Sn. Cl or Br.	Pt-OH. Alkali.	Sn. Cl or Br.	Pt-OH. Alkali.		
Sn(OPr) ₄ , Pt-OH (2.96 g.) CH ₃ COBr (1.77 g.) benzene (24.0 g.)	1 : 2	SnBr ₄ (OPr) ₄ , Pt-OH (8.1 g.) white solid	27.0	..	25.9	24.9	..	..
Sn(OPr) ₄ , Pt-OH (2.3 g.) CH ₃ COBr (2.02 g.) benzene (26.0 g.)	1 : 3	SnBr ₄ OPt, Pt-OH (2.6 g.) white solid	26.0	..	24.9	50.1	..	..
Sn(OPr) ₄ , Pt-OH (3.31 g.) CH ₃ COBr (3.32 g.) benzene (27.0 g.)	1 : 4	SnBr ₄ (2.9 g.) colorless liquid	27.1	..	27.1	72.9	..	..
Sn(OPr) ₄ , Pt-OH (1.78 g.) CH ₃ COBr (3.2 g.) benzene (18.0 g.)	1 : 6	SnBr ₄ (1.8 g.) colorless liquid	27.0	..	27.1	72.9	..	..
Sn(OEt) ₄ (5.5 g.) CH ₃ COCl (5.5 g.) benzene (26.0 g.)	1 : 4	SnCl ₄ , ZEtOAc (9.1 g.) brown viscous liquid	27.0	..	27.1	32.4	..	Distilled (90%) at 37°/0.1 mm.

* The isopropanol content was determined by careful fractionation of the binary azeotrope (C₃H₇-EtOH) from isopropyl acetate in a hydrolysed sample. As isopropyl acetate is oxidised by chromic acid, the analytical result was verified by a blank experiment with stannic chloride and isopropyl acetate mixture.

(80 g.) was refluxed and then rendered free of alcohol as before to afford a crystalline solid (3.6 g.). [Found: Sn, 30.3; Cl, 9.1; PrⁱOH, 60.8. SnCl(OPrⁱ)₃PrⁱOH requires Sn, 30.3; Cl, 9.05; PrⁱOH, 61.1%]. The analysis of the product remained substantially unaltered on repeated crystallisation from isopropanol in which the dichloride product was too soluble for proper crystallisation from even highly concentrated solutions.

Reaction of Stannic Chloride with t-Butyl Acetate.—A mixture of stannic chloride (0.62 g.) and excess of *t*-butyl acetate was refluxed (90°) for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. when a white solid (0.6 g.) was left after evacuating the excess ester. [Found: Sn, 38.6; Cl, 22.1; alkali, 3.90 moles. SnCl₄(OOCCH₃)₂ requires Sn, 38.5; Cl, 23.04%; alkali, 4.0 moles].

The financial support from the University Grants Commission to one of the authors (V.D.G.) as fellowship is gratefully acknowledged.

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Received January 19, 1965.